

SANCTIONS TO PREVENT CORRUPTION

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Today, large-scale reforms are being carried out to prevent corruption-related crimes. In particular, systematic measures are being taken to improve the legal awareness and legal culture of the population, and to form an intolerant attitude towards corruption in society.

Undoubtedly, these reforms are bearing fruit. In particular, in the Rule of Law Index of the World Justice Project "Freedom from Corruption" in 2019, Uzbekistan took 95th place with 0.38 points, and in 2020 it took 89th place among 128 countries with 0.40 points and rose to 6th place. the result of systemic reforms [1].

At the same time, legal measures to prevent corruption crimes have a positive impact, and legal actions to prevent corruption crimes mean the prevention and commission of socially dangerous acts (actions or inactions) recognized as offenses or crimes containing signs of corruption. - education of the individual and awakening of remorse for a socially dangerous act (action or inaction), recognized as an offense or a crime committed, is a means of influence aimed at compensating for material or non-material damage caused to the state and society.

Such measures of influence are divided into separate types depending on the type, volume and content of a socially dangerous act (action or inaction), recognized as an offense or a crime that has been committed or may be committed:

Socio-political impact measures related to state reforms;

Disciplinary measures;

Measures of administrative and legal influence;

Criminological and preventive measures;

Criminal law measures

such as criminal justice measures are the most powerful measures to prevent corruption offences.

Criminal remedies are criminal remedies to educate perpetrators of crimes under the Criminal Code and force them to repent or refrain from planning a crime.

At the same time, criminal law measures can be divided into several types, namely:

Measure of responsibility for a specific act;

A measure of appropriate punishment for persons who have committed a specific crime;

Other measures of coercion are applied to persons who have committed a specific crime.

Measures of a criminal law nature can be seen in the section on disposition and sanctions of the norms of the Criminal Code of the Russian Federation, where the disposition provides for responsibility, and the sanction provides for punishment and other measures of influence.

First of all, in relation to the measure of responsibility for a specific act, according to Article 16 of the Criminal Code of the Russian Federation, criminal liability is the legal consequence of a crime for which the court passes a guilty verdict, imposes a punishment or other measure prescribed by law. guilty of a crime [2]. At the same time, the commission of an act that has all the signs of a crime under the Criminal Code of the Russian Federation is the basis for bringing to responsibility.

There are a number of concepts related to the concept of criminal liability, in particular, according to M. Usmonaliev, criminal liability is a criminal relationship between a person and the state for committing an act prohibited by the Criminal Code [3].

According to M. Rustambaev, criminal liability is a form of legal liability, which is determined by criminal law and applied by the court to a person guilty of a crime [4].

According to article 42 of the Criminal Code of the Russian Federation, a measure of coercion is applied to the conviction of a person for a crime, imposed on behalf of the state by depriving or restricting certain rights and freedoms provided for by law.

The law provides for basic and additional punishments, and B.M. According to Leontiev, the main punishment is a punishment applied only to oneself, supplementing or not supplementing other punishments, and to achieve the main goal of punishment, and additional punishment is a punishment that has an auxiliary value for achieving the goal. this punishment [5].

Although responsibility and punishment are separate concepts, it is necessary to bring the perpetrator to justice and impose punishment only on the person who committed the act, if the specific act contains signs of a crime and the act is recognized as a crime.

The Criminal Code provides for several types of punitive measures, and according to article 43 of the Criminal Code, these are:

- a) a fine;
- b) deprivation of certain rights;
- b1) compulsory public works;
- c) correctional work;
- d) service restrictions;
- d1) restriction of freedom;
- e) referral to a disciplinary unit;
- j) deprivation of liberty;
- h) life imprisonment.

In addition to the main punishment, additional punishment may be applied to convicts in the form of deprivation of military or special rank.

Penalties in the form of restriction in service or transfer to a disciplinary unit apply only to military personnel.

Deprivation of a certain right can be applied not only as the main punishment, but also as an additional one.

Almost all types of punishments listed for corruption offenses are applied in an alternative way, the purpose of which is the education and prevention of corruption offenses, as well as the imposition of legal sanctions on the perpetrator and the perpetrator.

In addition, other measures of coercion are included in the list of criminal penalties, and the current Criminal Code applies coercive measures to adults and minors. However, according to article 17 of the Criminal Code, the subject of corruption offenses is a person who has reached the age of 18, so below we will talk about coercive measures applied to adults.

With regard to adults, Chapter 18 of the Criminal Code provides for the application of only coercive medical measures. The court may apply compulsory medical measures to a person whose mental state has deteriorated in such a way that he is unable to control if he represents a danger to society due to his mental state and the nature of the act committed.

If we analyze the system of punishments for corruption crimes from the point of view of the legislation of foreign countries, we can see that there are norms that differ from our legislation.

In particular, under Swiss criminal law, persons who commit a crime using their official powers can be dismissed.

Under article 323 of the Italian Penal Code, abuse of office is punishable by up to 4 years' imprisonment, and under article 28 of the German Penal Code, an official is punishable by up to 15 years' imprisonment for abuse of office.

According to the first paragraph of article 220 of the Criminal Code of the State of Bosnia and Herzegovina, a serious violation of the rights of another person by abuse of official position or powers exceeding his official powers is punishable by imprisonment for a term of six to five years.

According to article 359 (1) of the Serbian Criminal Code, if an official abuses his official position or power, illegally increases his property, causes serious damage to the interests of the state and citizens by deliberately evading official duties, a period of six months to five years will be concluded in prison.

We can also see that in some foreign countries administrative liability has been established for less significant manifestations of corruption. In particular, under the legislation of Kazakhstan, it is not a crime for an official to accept or donate as a gift property, property rights or other property interests in an amount not exceeding two monthly calculation indices, without prior consent to commit an action (inaction) within his competence, is the basis for bringing to administrative or disciplinary responsibility.

Based on the above analysis, it can be concluded that the listed criminal sanctions are an important tool for an uncompromising fight against corruption, and these sanctions should be improved taking into account the experience of developed countries.

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